

Ex SPSS Trainer with 12 years of experience in Statistics and Data Mining

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Built 10 over prediction models in a local Telco to profile, find next product to purchase and understand what Telco products to sell to customers based on URL and App browsing behaviour

2. Aim

To find potential customers who will use more mobile data, extend their services to paid TV and broadband and their URL and App browsing behaviour

3. Material and methods

The prediction models which are running live now on targeted campaigns are

1. C5 decision tree for profiling and predict
2. APRIORI which predicts the TV channels they will purchase based on the mobile services they are using.
3. K-means to group the customers' URL and App Genre to know their URL and Apps browsing behaviour.

4. Results

The prediction models are going live and earning more revenue for the Telco and scoring their customers 24/7

5. Conclusions

This also allows their marketing team to mix and match prediction targets strategies for customized selling which in turns increases their ROI and competitiveness in the Telco market.

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6. Keywords

Prediction, Big Data, Decision Tree, Clustering, Market Basket Analysis

Author biography

Jarrold Jarrod is an ex SPSS trainer who has 12 years of experience in building prediction models. He had experiences in building prediction models in banking, insurance, Government, e-commerce, Telco and mobile phone industry. As he was an SPSS trainer, he had taught Statistics and Data Mining for 3 years to 3,000 over professionals.